

Study of Sleep and Effects on Adolescents**Deepty Kumar¹, Gurmeet Kaur², Jugesh Chhatwal³, Krisnanand Chaudhary⁴, Gourav Claudius⁵**¹Consultant, Pediatrician & Neonatologist, Bethany Hospital, Thane²Professor, Dept. of Pediatrics, Christian Medical College, Ludhiana³Professor, Dept. of Pediatrics, Christian Medical College, Ludhiana⁴Professor, Dept. of Psychiatry, Christian Medical College, Ludhiana⁵Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pediatrics, LSLAM Government Medical College, Raigarh

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Deepty Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Adolescence is a critical period of transition from childhood to adulthood, during which sleep patterns change significantly. Adequate sleep is essential for promoting healthy development, cognitive function, and psychosocial well-being. This study aimed to assess the sleep patterns and their effects on adolescents.**Method:** A cross-sectional, self-reported survey was conducted among 1,000 adolescents (middle and late adolescents) of both genders. Adolescents with chronic illness or medication affecting sleep were excluded. Data were analyzed using T-test, Chi-square test, Z test, regression analysis, and ANOVA**Results:** 56.7% of adolescents reported good sleep quality, 30.6% satisfactory, and 12.7% poor sleep quality. Late adolescents (16.3%) and girls (16.1%) experienced poorer sleep quality compared to their peers. Nocturnal awakenings occurred in 11.8% of subjects, with higher occurrences among girls (29.1%) and late adolescents (34.5%). Daytime sleepiness was reported by 10.1%, and 38.2% took daytime naps. Notably, those experiencing nocturnal awakenings were more likely to report daytime sleepiness. Factors like mobile phone use, coffee and coke consumption negatively impacted sleep quality. Furthermore, poor sleep quality was associated with lower academic performance, while satisfactory sleep had a positive influence on scholastic success.**Conclusion:** These findings highlight the need to promote healthy sleep habits among adolescents to support their development and academic performance.**Keywords:** Adolescent, Sleep Quality, Cell Phone Usage, Scholastic Performance.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Sleep affects physical growth, behavior and emotional development besides determining cognitive functioning, learning and attention [1]. Sleep/wake patterns change throughout life. In particular, childhood sleep patterns change dramatically from preadolescence to adolescence [2]. Circadian rhythms or biological sleep patterns among adolescents are thought to be different from those of preadolescents or adults [3]. Adolescents prefer to go to sleep later at night and wake up later in the day, a pattern not typically seen among preadolescents and older adults [3].

Sleep requirements that range from 8.5 to 9.25 hours are observed in adolescent age group [4] however, adolescent obtain less sleep than required. Sleep disturbance may occur in as 11 to 30 % of adolescents [4]. Chronic partial sleep loss has negative effects on neurocognitive performance, mood, and health [5]. A large survey of 12- to 15-year-old subjects showed correlations between

sleep problems, rebelliousness, depressive symptoms, and cigarette smoking [6]. Sleep deprivation among adolescents causes an increase in inattentive behavior and daytime sleepiness may affect mood, behavior, and academic performance and even put adolescents at risk for accidents or injury [5].

A cross-sectional study done among Indian urban school going adolescents concluded -Adolescents of higher Grades had lesser sleep time, and frequent awakenings; suffered daytime leg pain, and felt sleepy during the day.

These factors suggest increasing sleep deprivation among higher Graders. [7] Understanding the huge detrimental effects of loss of sleep among growing adolescents, and considering the need to emphasize the important yet ignored subject this study was planned with the objective of assessing the sleep habits and its effects of the urban adolescents.

Methodology

The study was conducted as a questionnaire-based survey with age range of 14 to 19 of both gender attending school and college catering to middle and upper socioeconomic group in metropolitan city in northern India. Objective of the study was to study sleep pattern and its affects among the middle and late adolescents (14-19 years). A total of 1000 adolescents were included in the study. The verbal consent was taken from the subjects. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses to all the questions. The subjects with physical illness like asthma, chronic sinusitis, recurrent abdominal pain, chronic back ache,

seizure disorder, known cases of hypothyroidism, diabetes or any other chronic illness or use of medication which are known to affect sleep were excluded from the study. The data was collected and analysed using T-test, Chi-square test, Z test, regression analysis, and ANOVA test where applicable.

Results

Out of the Total Study Subjects 562 (56.2%) were Boys and 438(43.8%) were Girls. Among them 66.7 % were middle adolescent (14-16 years) and significantly a smaller number of 33.3% were late adolescent (17-19 Years)

Figure 1: Gender distribution of Participants

More than half of the adolescents (56.7%) reported having good sleep quality, followed by 30.6% who rated their sleep as satisfactory, and 12.7% who reported poor sleep quality. When comparing two age groups, a significantly higher percentage of late

adolescents (16.3%) reported poor sleep quality compared to middle adolescents (10.9%). Additionally, a significantly higher percentage of girls (16.1%) reported poor sleep quality compared to boys (9.9%).

Table 1: Quality of sleep of the subjects according to age and gender

		Total number	Poor	Satisfactory	Good
Age groups	Total	998	127(12.7)	305(30.6)	566(56.7)
	Middle Adolescent	667	73(10.9)	213(31.9)	381(57.1)
	Late adolescent	331	54(16.3)	92(27.8)	185(56.7)
Gender groups	Total	1003	127(12.7)	307(30.6)	569(56.7)
	Boys	563	56(9.9)	187(33.2)	320(56.8)
	Girls	440	71(16.1)	120(27.3)	249(56.6)

Figures in bracket indicates percentages, for age group $\chi=6.312$, $p=0.043$, significant for gender group $\chi=10.325$, $p=.006$, significant

The majority of subjects (72.2%) did not experience nocturnal awakenings. However, a higher percentage of late adolescents (34.5%) reported nocturnal awakenings compared to middle adolescents (24.4%), a difference that was statistically significant ($p=0.001$). When comparing genders, more girls (29.1%) reported experiencing nocturnal awakenings than boys (26.8%), though this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.441$). Out of the total study participants, 10.1% reported experiencing daytime sleepiness.

Middle adolescents reported a significantly higher rate of daytime sleepiness (11.6%) compared to late adolescents (7.1%). In terms of gender, boys reported a higher percentage of daytime sleepiness (12.6%) compared to girls (6.8%), with the difference being statistically significant ($p=0.003$). A greater proportion of subjects who experienced daytime sleepiness also reported nocturnal awakenings (13.4%) compared to those without nocturnal awakenings (9.5%), though this difference was not statistically significant

Table 2: Personal cell phones and quality of sleep

Personal cell phones and quality of sleep					
		Total number	No	Yes	P value
Quality of sleep	Total	1003	256(25.5)	747(74.5)	.003
	Poor	127	33(26)	94(74)	
	Satisfactory	709	163(23)	546(77)	
	Good	167	60(35.9)	107(64.1)	

For Age $\chi^2 = 11.91$, $p = .003$, significant

In our study, 74.5% of adolescents had personal cell phones. Good sleepers were less likely to own phones (64.1%) compared to poor sleepers (74%) and those with satisfactory sleep (77%), showing a clear relationship between phone ownership and sleep quality $p = .003$. Significantly higher number of good (54.3%) and satisfactory (38.2%) sleepers

in comparison to poor sleepers (25.6%) never drink coffee per day $p = .000$. Significantly higher number of good (48.2%) and satisfactory (64.4%) sleepers in comparison to poor sleepers (38.6%) never drink coke per day $p = .000$. The study shows that possession of a mobile phone, drinking coffee and coke had a negative effect on the quality of sleep.

Table 3: Scholastic performance and quality of sleep

Grades					
		Total	unsatisfactory	satisfactory	P value
Quality of sleep	Total	1003	256(25.5)	747(74.5)	.001
	Poor	127	33(26)	94(74)	
	Satisfactory	709	163(23)	546(77)	
	Good	167	60(35.9)	107(64.1)	

Out of the total subjects (74.5%) had satisfactory grade, among those who have satisfactory sleep (77%) subjects had satisfactory grade in comparison to poor Sleepers (74%) $p = 0.001$. Our study shows satisfactory sleep had a positive effect on scholastic performance.

Discussion

A total of 1000 subjects participated in the study out of which two third 66.7% were middle adolescent and one third 33.3% were late adolescents, and almost equal number of boys (56.2%) and Girls (43.8%) were studied. This distribution is similar to another study In India by Gupta et al and in Iran by Ghanizadeh et al [7, 8]. In our study, the mean sleep duration of middle adolescents is 7.2 ± 1.65 hours on weekdays and 8.8 ± 2.04 hours on weekends. Mean sleep duration of late adolescents on weekdays is 6.8 ± 1.42 hours on weekdays and 8.3 ± 2.07 hours on weekends. In a study by Ghanizadeh et al among adolescents done in Iran also reported Mean duration of night sleep as 7.7 hours. [8]

In our study we saw that majority (27.8%) of subjects have nocturnal awakening. A higher number (34.5%) of late adolescent as compared to (24.4%) of middle adolescent have nocturnal awakening and the difference is statistically significant $p = 0.001$. No significant gender difference was seen. The results are similar to Indian study by, Gupta et al where nocturnal awakening was seen in mean of 37% of adolescents

(9, 10, 11, 12, grades, 35.9% 44.7%, 40.3% and 44.3% $p (0.001)$. [7] In the present study (38.2%) of total subjects reported daytime napping. Between the two genders higher percentage of boys (45.1%) in comparison to Girls have napping habit. This difference was significant $p = 0.009$. In the study done by Gupta et al also reported day time napping in (47.6%) 9th graders, (50.4%) 10th graders, (61.8%) 11th graders, and (69.8%) 12th graders ($p = 0.001$). [7] More than half of adolescent (56.7%) have good sleep quality, followed by 30.6% adolescents reporting satisfactory sleep quality and 12.7% adolescent have poor sleep quality. Among two age groups, a significantly higher percentage (16.3%) of late adolescents as compared to (10.9%) middle adolescents have reported poor sleep quality, ($p = 0.043$) and a significantly higher percentage of girls (55.9%) as compared to 44.1% of boys reported poor sleep quality ($p = .006$). Liu et al studied on Chinese adolescents reported that 18.8% studies have shown similar percentage of poor sleepers among adolescents [1]. Yang et al also reported majority (81.7%) of subjects reported sleep quality as good and excellent, 18.8% reported poor sleep quality [2].

Out of the total subjects in our study, 74.5% adolescent have personal cellular phones. Lowest percentage (64.1%) of good sleeper as compared to (74%) poor and satisfactory (77%) sleepers possessed cellular phones. Yang et al (2010) reported positive correlation between electronic devices and insomnia and short nocturnal sleep

duration in adolescents [2]. Sivagurunathan P and Rafique N also reported that mobile phone use significantly affect quality of sleep among students [9, 10]. The study also shows that drinking coffee and coke had a negative effect on the quality of sleep. In the study done by Pollack et al (2003) on caffeine intake, they reported that high caffeine intake in general was associated with shorter nocturnal sleep duration, increased wake time after sleep onset, and increased daytime sleep [11]. In our study out of the total study subjects 10.1% reported daytime sleepiness, middle adolescent reported significantly higher 11.6% of daytime sleepiness as compared to late adolescent (7.1%). Gupta et al (2008) also reported daytime sleepiness in 37.2% in 9th graders, 39.1% in 10th graders, 39.7% in 11th graders and 54.2% in 12th graders (p0.001) which is higher than present study subjects [7]. Majority of students with satisfactory grades (77%) have satisfactory quality of sleep compared to 74% poor sleeper and 64% good sleeper (p = 0.001). Shin C et al (2003) and Wolfson et al in their studies also reported satisfactory quality of sleep positively affects scholastic performance which is similar to our study [12, 13]. So our study also concludes that Sleep impacts academic performance [14]

Conclusion

This study highlights a significant concern regarding inadequate sleep among adolescents. Middle adolescents (ages 14-16) reported sleeping 7-8 hours on weekdays, while late adolescents slept even less, averaging 6.8 hours on school nights, leading to a considerable sleep debt. Although a majority of adolescents reported good sleep quality, a notable proportion particularly late adolescents and girls experienced poor sleep quality. Factors such as mobile phone use and the consumption of coffee and coke were identified as having a negative impact on sleep. Importantly, good sleep quality was linked to better academic performance, while poor sleep quality was associated with negative academic outcomes. These findings emphasize the need to promote healthy sleep habits among adolescents to support their academic success and overall well-being.

Acknowledgements: We sincerely thank to all the adolescents who actively participated and cooperated in the study

References

1. Liu X, Liu L, Owens JA, Kaplan DL. Sleep patterns and sleep problems among schoolchild-

dren in the United States and China. *Pediatrics*. 2005; 115(1 Suppl):241-9.

2. Yang YS, Yen JY, Ko CH, Cheng CP, Yen CF. The association between problematic cellular phone use and risky behaviors and low self-esteem among Taiwanese adolescents. *BMC public health*. 2010; 10:217.
3. Carskadon MA. Patterns of sleep and sleepiness in adolescents. *Pediatrician*. 1990; 17(1):5-12.
4. Glaze DG. Childhood insomnia *Sleep Medicine Pediatr Clin N Am*. 2004; 51:33 -50.
5. Hansen M, Janssen I, Schiff A, Zee PC, Dubocovich ML. The impact of school daily schedule on adolescent sleep. *Pediatrics*. 2005; 115(6):1555-61.
6. Patten CA, Choi WS, Gillin JC, Pierce JP. Depressive symptoms and cigarette smoking predict development and persistence of sleep problems in US adolescents. *Pediatrics*. 2000; 106(2):E23.
7. Gupta R, Bhatia MS, Chhabra V, Sharma S, Dahiya D, Semalti K, et al. Sleep patterns of urban school-going adolescents. *Indian Pediatr*. 2008; 45(3):183-9.
8. Ghanizadeh A, Kianpoor M, Rezaei M, Rezaei H, Moini R, Aghakhani K, et al. Sleep patterns and habits in high school students in Iran. *Annals of general psychiatry*. 2008; 7:5.
9. Sivagurunathan P, Vaithilingan S, Vinothkumar R. Restriction of Mobile Phone Usage at Bed Time: Effect on Sleep Quality, Mood and Cognitive Function. *National Journal of Community Medicine*. 2024; 15(10):785-91.
10. Rafique N, Al-Asoom LI, Alsunni AA, Saudagar FN, Almulhim L, Alkaltham G. Effects of Mobile Use on Subjective Sleep Quality. *Nature and science of sleep*. 2020; 12:357-64.
11. Pollak CP, Bright D. Caffeine consumption and weekly sleep patterns in US seventh-, eighth-, and ninth-graders. *Pediatrics*. 2003; 111(1):42-6.
12. Shin C, Kim J, Lee S, Ahn Y, Joo S. Sleep habits, excessive daytime sleepiness and school performance in high school students. *Psychiatry and clinical neurosciences*. 2003; 57(4):451-3.
13. Wolfson AR, Carskadon MA. Understanding adolescents' sleep patterns and school performance: a critical appraisal. *Sleep medicine reviews*. 2003; 7(6):491-506.
14. Hershner S. Sleep and academic performance: measuring the impact of sleep. *Current opinion in behavioral sciences*. 2020; 33:51-6.